

Exploring Science Discourse through Natural Language Processing

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Abstract. In this paper, we apply natural language processing (NLP) techniques to the area of discourse processes in middle school science classrooms. Employing similar methods to those used by Liu and Cohen (2021), we analyzed transcripts of middle school science classes using text-as-data methods to better understand turn-taking, targeting, use of analytic and social language, language coordination, questioning, and use of academic and routine language. Drawing on insights from engagement research, hybridity theory, and sociocultural theory, this approach allows us to detect important insights about discourse processes and teacher practices in urban middle school science classrooms.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing, Classroom Discourse, Science Education.

1 Introduction

The purpose of this study is to explore applications of natural language processing (NLP), a computer-assisted analytical technique aimed to automatically process, analyze, and comprehend textual data (Liu & Cohen, 2021; Manning et al., 1999) for providing new insights into science classroom discourse processes, including how agency is distributed among the teachers and their students and how students engage in science talk (e.g., Patall et al., 2019; Stroupe, 2014). Natural language processing offers a sophisticated and powerful way to analyze talk patterns in classrooms other than using time-intensive hand coding.

Research shows that classrooms where students funds of knowledge (historically rooted and culturally developed knowledge and skills) are integrated into discourse increase engagement and learning in science, especially among historically minoritized students. In this study, we examine transcripts from classroom videos in urban middle school science classrooms in order to better understand:

1. How authority is distributed across discourse spaces in middle school science classrooms.
2. How teachers and students in middle school science classrooms engage in science talk.

To do this, we replicate NLP text-as-data analyses run by Liu and Cohen (2021) to investigate turn-taking, targeting, use of analytic and social language, language coordination, questioning, and use of academic and routine language. Our findings have implications for the study of classroom discourse and teacher practices, as well as for the future of NLP in classroom discourse research.

2 Data

2.1 Participants, Classroom Videos and Transcription

Participants in this study consisted of a total of 101 middle school students (grades 6 to 8) from seven urban classrooms across six schools in two school divisions in the southeastern region of the U.S. were included (Kim, 2005; Kline, 2015). Students were recruited based on their teachers' consent to participate in a larger science education project. The sample represented a diverse student population, consisting of 51.5% female and 44.6% male, 15.8% White, 38.6% Black/African American, 17.8% Hispanic/Latinx, and 21.8% Mixed Race, 5% Asian/Pacific Islander, and 1.0% Native American. Students' mean age was 12.66 years old ($SD = 0.92$).

A total of 7 science classroom were collected using the Swivl technology, which includes a camera that captures a wide-angle view of the teacher and students. The classroom teacher wore a wireless microphone and audio recorders were placed on student tables to capture student voices. The videos ranged from 38.97 to 77.98 ($M = 58.09$, $SD = 14.44$) minutes in length. The main analytic sample for this NLP study was the verbatim transcriptions of the videos, and the unit of analysis was marked by the beginning and end of each speaker's (teacher versus student) turn (Liu & Cohen, 2021).

3 Natural Language Processing Analysis

3.1 Authority

To answer our first research question, we followed the example of Liu and Cohen (2021) and ran several analyses that would allow us to examine authority in the classrooms studied. First, we calculated words spoken per minute for teachers and students, these were 69.29% and 30.71% respectively. This was followed by analysis of targeting, which is when people target specific individuals (including themselves) in the discussion, which we calculated by use of personal pronouns like "you" and "I", a dimension which is also known to relate to social status, with higher social status individuals using "you" more frequently and lower social status individuals using "I" more frequently (Pennebaker, 2011). We found that "you" was used by teachers 72.3% of times

it appeared in text, vs. 24.7% use by students, whereas “I” usage was 68.3% students to 31.7% teacher.

Following these analyses, we ran an LIWC (Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count) clout analysis. LIWC analyses identify words that are associated with constructs or dimensions. The clout algorithm we use was developed based on results of studies using data of people interacting with each other (e.g., Kacewicz et al., 2014) and is used to analyze the relative social status, confidence, or leadership that people display through their writing or in this case, talking. Use of words like “you” and “we”, for instance, generally indicate a higher status than words like “I”. Across our sample, teachers had a mean score of 68.63, while students had a mean score of 41.67, indicating that teachers exerted much more clout in the classroom than students.

3.2 Science Discourse

Table 1. Words spoken by teachers and students (%)

Class	Teacher	Student	Total #words	% Teacher words	% Student words
1	6324	2076	8400	75.29%	24.71%
2	1223	4257	5480	22.32%	77.68%
3	4401	1263	5664	77.70%	22.30%
4	1614	192	1806	89.37%	10.63%
5	1876	320	2196	85.43%	14.57%
6	4720	700	5420	87.08%	12.92%
7	4733	2225	6958	68.02%	31.98%
Total	24891	11033	35924	69.29%	30.71%

Linguistic Styles

The next set of analyses we ran were intended to give us a sophisticated understanding of the type of language that teachers and students use while talking about science. We ran a LIWC analysis on social and analytic language, with analytic language characterized by words involving formal, logical and hierarchical thinking, while social language refers to human interaction. We found that students used analytic language 40.94% of the time compared to teachers 25.55%, and social words 10.94% of the time compared to teachers 16.49%. This may indicate that teachers need to use social language to manage discourse spaces, while students need to use analytic language to answer questions and talk about science.

Our next analysis tested language coordination using language style matching, which tests how frequently two people in conversation match speaking behavior or style a higher score indicates a better coordination throughout the conversation. Students in a classroom were grouped together and treated as one party in the analysis, and teachers were treated as another. Our results range from .76 to .91 on a scale of 0 to 1, indicating varying but generally high coordination.

Questioning

To test frequency of open ended vs. closed ended questions, we first had a trained coders hand-code questions in our dataset as open or closed ended, and then separated the data into a training and test dataset. We then used a LASSO algorithm on the training dataset to identify open and closed ended questions, and then tested it on the test data set. Our model had an accuracy rate of .933, identifying 156 open ended question with 8 wrong predictions, and 86 closed ended questions with 16 wrong predictions. With an accuracy this high, we believe this algorithm can be used to label questions in future datasets.

Academic vs. Routine Language

To test use of academic vs. routine language in our sample, we used topic modeling to identify science and routine language. Our algorithm used science dictionaries from Word Domains (<https://wndomains.fbk.eu/hierarchy.html>) with the following domain words: physics, astronomy, earth, biology, and mathematics to identify science words. Results showed that across the 7 classrooms, science teacher spoken words (24,891 words, see Table 1 for class breakdown) consisted of 69.29% of science discourse compared to 30.71% student spoken words (11,033). The proportion of teacher versus student spoken science words (consisting of approximately 20% of all words spoken) followed similar trends, with 68.33% of the science words being spoken by the teacher, and 31.67% of the science words being spoken by the students. These findings indicate that teachers control the majority of science talk in classrooms, both in terms of the quantity and quality of words spoken.

Table 2. Science words spoken (%)

Class	Teacher	Student	Total #science words	% Teacher science words	% Student science words
1	1139	425	1564	72.83%	27.17%
2	217	777	994	21.83%	78.17%
3	721	206	927	77.78%	22.22%
4	212	30	242	87.60%	12.40%
5	291	53	344	84.59%	15.41%
6	962	145	1107	86.90%	13.10%
7	999	469	1468	68.05%	31.95%
Total	4541	2105	6646	68.33%	31.67%

4 Discussion

Emerging trends demonstrate that teachers are largely driving classroom discourse, both in the number of science words spoken, as well in initiating discussion. These findings have implications for targeting specific discourse opportunities and shifting agency to students connected to students' everyday lexicons, and for future use of NLP to analyze classroom discourse.

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